

国家纳米科学中心

National Center for Nanoscience and Technology

High Performance Shape Memory Composites and Their 3-D Printing

Zhong Zhang*

National Center for Nanoscience and Technology, China

国家纳米科学中心

www.nanoctr.cn

Smart Materials

Smart wing structure (upper left), artist's concept of solar sail (lower left) and 4-D printing (3-D printing of smart materials) (right).

Shape Memory Polymer Composites

Triple shape memory effects of chemically crosslinked polyolefin blends: permanent shape (a) → 1st temporary shape (b) → 2nd temporary shape (c) → 1st temporary shape (d) → permanent shape (e).

Zhao J., et al. ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces, 2013, 5, 5550.

Electrically driven triple shape memory effects of chemically crosslinked polyolefin blends (left) and SEM images showing selective localization of CNT in one phase of cocontinuous structure (right).

Wang, Z. et al. ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces, 2014, 6, 20051.

3-D Printing

Fused deposition printing
Solid
No direct crosslinking network

Photocurable printing
Liquid
Photo-curable groups

Direct-writing printing
High-viscosity liquid
Direct crosslinking, shape memory

1. High performance shape memory polymer composites

- Polyolefin with functional surfaces
- Epoxy with high modulus
- Polyurethane with near-body temperature switch

2. 3-D printing of shape memory polymer composites

- Fused deposition printing of polyolefin
- Epoxy and its friction and wear properties
- Direct writing of PU

3. Conclusions and outlook

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1) Polyolefin

Natural surfaces

Natur. Rev. Mater., 2017, 2, 17036.

Materials

Polymer: Poly(cyclic octene) (PCO)

Crosslinking: Chemically by peroxide

Chemical crosslinking

Controlling the thermal and mechanical properties by adjusting the crosslinker.

Shape memory effect

Shape memory properties of various samples

Samples	0.5-5	0.5-10	0.5-20	2.0-5	2.0-10	2.0-20
R_f (%)	72.5	97.5	97.2	97.6	98.0	95.8
R_r (%)	0	96.9	97.6	83.9	92.9	92.8

3-D shape memory effect of 0.5-20-cPCO

Large recoverable strain: 730%

deformation

recovery

Functional surfaces

The wettability of material surface is determined by both chemical composition and surface structure.

Wenzel model $\cos \theta_w = r \cos \theta$

Cassie model

$$\cos \theta_c = f \cos \theta + (1 - f) \cos \pi = f(1 + \cos \theta) - 1$$

Theoretical calculations

$$\cos \theta_c = f \cos \theta + (1 - f) \cos \pi = f(1 + \cos \theta) - 1$$

$$f = \frac{1 + \cos \theta_c}{1 + \cos \theta}$$

$$f' = 1 - \frac{a'a''}{(a' + b')(a'' + b'')}$$

$$f'' = 1 - k \frac{a'a''}{(a' + b')(a'' + b'')}$$

a' and a'' : Side length of grooves parallel and vertical to the tensile direction

b' and b'' : Groove spacing parallel to and perpendicular to the drawing direction

k : Proportion of gas-liquid interface in grooves

$k \rightarrow 1$: close to the Cassie state

$k \rightarrow 0$: close to the Wenzel state

$$\theta_h = \theta_a - \theta_r$$

$$\theta_h = 20.1^\circ$$

$$\theta_h = 65.5^\circ$$

Effect of micro-nano surface patters

Effect of mico-nano surface patterns

Effect of temperature

Effect of stretching

Effect of temperature and time

Condensed water drop.

Hierarchical surface patterns

Larger surface:

- More exchange of matter and energy
- Larger storage capacity

Science, 2007, 317, 650.

Bilayer system

Energy principle:

$$U = \frac{1}{2} E_f h \varepsilon^2 - \frac{1}{4} E_f h \varepsilon k^2 A^2 + \frac{1}{48} E_f h^3 k^4 A^2 + \frac{1}{8} E_s k A^2 + \frac{1}{32} E_f h k^4 A^2$$

Theoretical simulation

Average total potential energy per unit length:

$$U = \frac{1}{2} E_f h \varepsilon^2 - \frac{1}{4} E_f h \varepsilon k^2 A^2 + \frac{1}{48} E_f h^3 k^4 A^2 + \frac{1}{8} E_s k A^2 + \frac{1}{32} E_f h k^4 A^2$$

Critical wavelength of film instability:

$$\lambda_c \approx 2\pi h \left(\frac{E_f}{E_s} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}}$$

Fourier transform: $\hat{u}(k) = \int \tilde{u}(x) \exp(-ikx) dx$

$\hat{w}(k) = \int w(x) \exp(-ikx) dx$

Iterative equation: $\hat{w}^{(m+1)} = \left[u + \left(\frac{k \bar{E}_s}{2 \bar{E}_f} + \frac{1}{12} \bar{k}^4 \right) dt \right]^{-1} \left[u \hat{w}^{(m)} + F(\bar{N} \bar{w}_{,xx}^{(m)}) dt \right]$

Until the displacement field tends to be stable, it is considered that the iteration ends and the equilibrium state is reached.

Simulation of Fourier Spectrum

Influencing factors:
Modulus ratio, film
thickness, strain

Zhao, L. et al. ACS Appl. Mater.
Interface, 2019, 11, 1563.¹⁶

Experimental processes

- ✓ Transforming the construction of three-dimensional structure into the preparation of two-dimensional thin films
- ✓ Introducing multi-dimensional regulation of time and space
- ✓ Large area

Prepared patterns

Zhao, L. et al. ACS Appl. Mater. Interface, 2019, 11, 1563.

Evolution of surface patterns

Sci. Rep. 2015, 5, 8887.

Effect of strain distribution and sequence

Effect of surface strain distribution

Effect of increasing strain in y axis direction

Application in pressure sensor

Composites with superior stiffness

Crosslinking degree $E \approx 3\rho RT/\overline{M}_c$ $\frac{E}{3RT} = \frac{\rho}{\overline{M}_c} = \frac{m}{V \times \overline{M}_c} = \frac{\overline{M}_c \times N}{V \times \overline{M}_c} = \frac{N}{V}$

	0.5EP	0.6EP	0.7EP	0.8EP	0.9EP	1.0EP	1.1EP	1.2EP
T_g (°C)	88	99	110	128	141	150	148	145
E' (MPa)	3.3	8.3	9.3	11.4	13.1	23.7	23.2	23.4
N (10^{-3} mol)	0.4	0.9	1.0	1.1	1.3	2.3	2.2	2.2

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Shape memory cycle and the mechanism

Increased strain and modulus

SMEP/MWCNT nanocomposites

Liu, Y. et al. ACS Appl. Mater. Interface, 2016, 8, 311.

Shape memory properties

Recovery force efficiency

Shape memory performance

SMEP/MWCNT nanocomposites have the best shape memory performance and stability

Improved mechanical properties

 SMEP/MWCNT
 Neat SMEP

SMEP/MWCNT nanocomposites show the fast recovery speed and fatigue resistance

Improved mechanical properties

Existing problem

An important problem neglected in the literature is that the modulus of polymers depends on temperature change, and the modulus of materials generally falls during shape transformation (One to two orders of magnitude), which will seriously change the practical performance.

Preparation

Discontinues system: SCF

Continues system: CF pre-preg and woven

The preparation process of SMEP/CF composites

Improved mechanical properties

Mechanism:
block the crack
propagation

Improved mechanical properties

Smart applications

Application exploration : SMEP composite blades

Blades preparation

Air flow velocity test

Blades deformation

Fixed

Theoretical simulation

The experimental and numerical simulation results for the air flow velocity with various shapes match well. These CFs reinforced SMEPCs are expected to be used as morphic smart structures in the fields of structural engineering.

3) Polyurethane (PU)

BTSMPU

Synthesis by reaction between -OH and -CNO with excessive -OH.

3 molecular structures.

Controlling the phase transition by adjusting the molecular weight.

Shape memory effect

Molecular structure.

Shape memory effect.

Shape memory properties

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Good shape memory effect.

Comparison with literature.

SMPU/GO nanocomposites

Recovery stress.

Elongation at break.

Degree of crosslinking (gel fraction)

Optically driving

Remote control

Bending

1D
↓
2D

Shape design.

Bending.

Response.

Opening box by light.

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1) Fused deposition printing of polyolefin

Objective

Fused Deposition Modeling (FDM)

- Simple process
- Low cost
- Composites
- Multifunction

Thermoplastic polymer

- Large deformation
- Flexible

Problem of PCO

Low modulus

- If printing in low temperature (110°C), the filament is difficult to extrude and easy to buckling.

- If printing in high temperature (240°C), it is difficult to cooling to T_m (55°C).

Solution 1

Improving the cooling rate using nitrogen.

Solution 2

Incorporation of BN to

- improve modulus
- improve cooling rate
- improve the recovery rate

Printing process

Shape design and electrical driving

2) Epoxy and its friction and wear properties

Direct-writing printing

Accuracy: 0.4 mm

Viscosity adjusting

Fiber orientation

Fiber orientation.

Wear and friction properties

Extrusion-induced SCF orientation

Wear and friction properties

XY

Z

ball-on-disk tests

Grinding ball surface

Scatched surface:

3) Direct-writing printing of PU

+MWCNTs

Planetary mixer

Partial coating

Direct-writing printing

4 wt% MWCNTs

Accuracy: 0.2 mm

1 layer

5 layers

8 layers

box

flower

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- ❑ **As a new type of smart materials, shape memory polymers have some outstanding advantages over traditional shape memory materials (alloys and ceramics). Most of their disadvantages can be overcome by adding inorganic or metallic fillers to prepare composites.**
- ❑ **3-D printing of shape memory polymer composites can help build up smart structures which is beneficial to the potential applications.**
- ❑ **To further improve the properties of shape memory polymer composites and realize wider real applications are still a big challenge for the researchers in this field.**

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thank you grazie **merci** danke **grazias** 謝謝 **спасибо**
gracias **obrigado** ありがとう **dank** takk **bedankt** dakujem

